

A comprehensive Evaluation Framework for Artificial Intelligence in Clinical Data Extraction and Normalization for Health Data Spaces

Analysis of 10 Multi-Center Cohorts in Diverse Therapeutic Areas

Gabriel Maeztu^{1,2,*}, Paula Chocron¹, Alejandro Castrelo¹, Sandra Pulido¹, Mónica Arrue¹, Flavius Nicu¹, Marc Oliver¹, Gustavo Mastroianni¹, María Quijada¹, Irene López¹, Marc Asenjo¹, Oriol Moles¹, Luis Leon¹, Laila Noya¹, Marcos Bautista¹, Mats Sundgren^{1,3}, Anna Nicolau⁴, Alvaro Abella⁵

Abstract

The effective extraction and normalization of clinical data are critical for advancing healthcare research and patient outcomes. In this study, we present a comprehensive evaluation framework for assessing artificial intelligence (AI) methodologies applied to clinical data extraction and normalization within Health Data Spaces. Leveraging the Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership Common Data Model (OMOP CDM) and advanced natural language processing (NLP) techniques, we conducted an evaluation and analysis across 10 multi-center cohorts encompassing diverse therapeutic areas.

The results demonstrate the efficacy of AI models in accurately extracting and normalizing clinical information, with validation metrics indicating significant improvements over traditional datasets. The evaluation across diverse cohorts shows the robustness and generalizability of the AI. The involvement of physicians in the evaluation of AI outputs, coupled with the assessment of inter-physician consensus and the reliability of their reviews, enhances the robustness and credibility of the results.

Keywords

Artificial Intelligence — Machine Learning — Natural Language Processing — Automated Terminology Mapping — Data Standards — OMOP CDM — Interoperability — Health Data Space — Real-World Data — Clinical Data Extraction — Data Validation — Data Verification

¹IOMED, Barcelona, Spain

²Universitat de Barcelona, Spain

³European Institute for Innovation through Health Data (i~HD), Gent, Belgium

⁴Neuroelectrics, Boston, USA

⁵Independent Researcher

*Contact details: g@iomed.health

Contents

1	Introduction	2
1.1	Background	2
1.2	Objective	3
2	Context	3
2.1	Key concepts	3
2.2	Overview of a Data Space Enablement process	4
2.3	Overview of the AI framework	5
	Continuous evaluation and enhancement of the AI framework	
2.4	AI capability evaluated in this study	6
	Automated Mapping Formula • Explicit Mention Formula	
3	Materials	7
3.1	Data Spaces	7
3.2	Cohorts	7
3.3	Performance metrics	8
	Verification metrics of the capabilities • Sample size determination for the verification metrics • Validation metrics of the data • Evaluation of the clinical annotators	
4	Methods	10
4.1	Quantitative analysis of the impact of AI-generated data points in the cohorts	11
	Comparative analysis of the downstream outcomes • Data Quality Assessment • Assessment of the volume and diversity of data • Individual Patient Data Completeness and Temporal Coverage	
4.2	Consistency of the AI capability evaluation metrics across Data Spaces and cohorts	13
	Intraclass Correlation Coefficient (ICC) • Coefficient of Variation (CV) • Levene's Test • Quantifying Center Variability in AI Performance via Bayesian Hierarchical Modeling • Meta-Analysis of Center Performance	
4.3	Inter-rater Reliability Analysis	15
	Fleiss' Kappa • Time per Task (TPT) Analysis • Agreement Score with the Golden Annotators	
5	Discussion	16
5.1	Limitations	17
5.2	Conclusion	17
	Acknowledgments	17
	References	17

1. Introduction

1.1 Background

The healthcare sector faces significant challenges in managing and utilizing vast amounts of clinical data. Approximately 60 to 80% of this data in real-world environments is unstructured [1], complicating direct analysis and scalability. This prevalence of unstructured data poses substantial obstacles to conducting comprehensive Real-World Evidence (RWE) studies, which are essential for medical research[2], patient outcomes, and health policy development[3].

In response to these challenges among others, the European

Health Data Space (EHDS) initiative aims to facilitate the exchange and access to diverse types of health data, supporting both healthcare delivery (primary use of data) and health research and policymaking (secondary use of data)[4]. The EHDS defines Data Spaces as repositories of health data maintained by Data Holders, entities such as hospitals, primary care providers, and other healthcare providers. These Data Holders are responsible for the maintenance and provision of access to the data.

Within this framework, Data Users, including researchers, policymakers, and healthcare providers, utilize Data Spaces to conduct RWE studies. The EHDS also defines the role of Data Mediators, entities that facilitate compliant data access and sharing between Data Users and Data Holders within the EU's legal framework. In the context of this study, IOMED functions as Data Mediators, providing a platform for the creation of Data Spaces. This role encompasses ensuring data governance, maintaining data quality, trustworthiness, interoperability, and facilitating secure access for Data Users while ensuring compliance with security and privacy regulations.

To effectively fulfill the role of Data Mediators and address the challenges posed by unstructured data, our team leverages Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies, particularly Natural Language Processing (NLP)[5] and Automated Terminology Mapping (ATM)[6]. These advanced technologies are crucial in bridging the gap between raw, unstructured clinical data and the standardized, interoperable format required for meaningful analysis and sharing within Data Spaces.

AI technologies offer substantial potential in enhancing the extraction, interpretation, and analysis of information from clinical notes and other free-text sources, enabling access to the vast amount of unstructured data [7, 8]. By employing NLP and ATM, our team can efficiently transform unstructured clinical narratives into structured, standardized data points that align with common data models and vocabularies used in healthcare research.

However, the implementation of AI in healthcare, particularly in the context of Data Mediation, necessitates rigorous methodological clarity and adherence to ethical standards. Challenges include ensuring data privacy, addressing biases in AI models, and maintaining transparency and explainability in AI-driven processes. Ethical considerations are paramount, especially concerning patient consent, data ownership, and compliance with regulations like the GDPR.

Technical integration of AI outputs into standardized data models within the Health Data Space requires sophisticated methods to ensure data quality and interoperability. This study evaluates 10 cohorts from 10 mediation processes, assessing the value and reliability of AI-generated data points in the integration process. Systematic evaluation of AI performance in real-world clinical settings is crucial, where accuracy, re-

producibility, and ethical considerations are paramount [9].

1.2 Objective

The primary objective of this study is to develop and validate a robust framework for the verification and validation of AI outputs in real-world clinical data integration. Specifically, the study aims to:

1. **Establish a Verification and Validation Process:** Develop a comprehensive methodology for physician-led verification and multi-dimensional validation of AI inferences.
2. **Demonstrate Generalizability and Reproducibility:** Showcase the framework's applicability across different therapeutic areas and geographic regions by validating AI outputs across 11 different cohorts from 10 hospitals across Europe, ensuring methodological rigor and consistency.

2. Context

2.1 Key concepts

Artificial Intelligence: Artificial Intelligence (AI) encompasses a suite of technologies that let computers execute a range of sophisticated tasks, such as visual perception, natural language understanding, translation and content generation, among other advanced functions.

Machine Learning: Machine Learning (ML) is a type of artificial intelligence. It involves creating algorithms that allow computers to learn from examples, which are usually sets of data. These algorithms can then make accurate predictions also called inferences on new unseen data. An example in the healthcare context would be identifying conditions or diseases in clinical texts or radiography images.

Natural Language Processing: Natural Language Processing (NLP) is a specialized branch of AI and ML focused on enabling machines to understand and interpret human language. NLP can be employed to process the vast amounts of unstructured textual data in medical records, extracting meaningful and structured clinical information. This capability is vital for transforming narrative patient records into actionable data.

Automated Terminology Mapping: Automated Terminology Mapping (ATM) is another branch of AI focus on automatically setting an identifier from a standardized terminology to records of data. This approach enables efficient and accurate comparison of large datasets of information from different sources of data as all are mapped to the same set of identifiers.

Evaluating ML Inferences: The evaluation process of ML inferences ensures that the conclusions drawn by these models

are accurate, reliable, and relevant. The complexity of medical data, with its nuances and variability, requires a comprehensive approach to the verification and validation, ensuring that ML outputs align with medical standards and practices.

Data Verification: The verification process involves a comparison of the output of the AI with the source of data.

Remote Source Data Verification (rSDV): Remote Source Data Verification (rSDV) is a method used to verify outputs against original data sources. It involves reviewing the original clinical notes to confirm the accuracy and relevance of data points, in the context of this paper, the AI outputs. For example, if an AI model identifies a diagnosis of diabetes, the physician checks the clinical notes used for this inference to ensure this diagnosis is correct. This process ensures that the data points generated by AI are accurate and reliable before they are integrated into the standardized database.

Data Validation: The validation process encompasses a systematic series of checks designed to detect unexpected trends, anomalies, and inconsistencies within the data. This step ensures that the conclusions derived from machine learning models are not only accurate and reliable at the micro level but also relevant at the macro level. Given the inherent complexity and variability of medical data, a comprehensive and meticulous approach to validation is imperative. This process involves cross-referencing AI-generated outputs with established medical standards and practices, thereby confirming that the machine learning outputs are consistent with clinical expectations and uphold the integrity of medical research.

European Health Data Space: The European Health Data Space (EHDS) initiative aims to facilitate the exchange and access to diverse types of health data, supporting both healthcare delivery (primary use of data) and health research and policymaking (secondary use of data)[4].

Data Holders: Data Holders are entities that maintain Data Spaces, including hospitals, primary care providers, and other healthcare providers.

Data Users: Data Users are entities that use Data Spaces, including researchers, policymakers, and healthcare providers.

Data Mediators: Data Mediators are entities that facilitate compliant data access and sharing between Data Users and Data Holders within the EU's legal framework.

Health Data Space: Health Data Space is a repository of health data maintained by Data Holders, including hospitals, primary care providers, and other healthcare providers.

Real-World Data: Real-World Data (RWD) in healthcare encompasses diverse data points collected from various sources, including Electronic Health Records (EHRs), medical claims,

patient registries, and more. This data provides a real-life snapshot of patient health, treatment outcomes, and health-care delivery, making it invaluable for research and clinical decision-making.

Data Model: A Data Model is a standardized framework that provides a common structure for data and vocabularies to enable interoperability and consistency in data across diverse datasets and systems.

Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics: The Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics (OHDSI) is a scientific alliance that aims to bring out the value of health data through large-scale analytics. OHDSI focuses on generating evidence that promotes better health decisions and better care. This community includes researchers, clinicians, industry experts, and other stakeholders who leverage open-source tools, standardized methodologies, and shared data in a scientifically rigorous manner to improve the understanding of diseases and health outcomes.

Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership Common Data Model and Vocabularies: Central to the OHDSI initiative is the Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership (OMOP) Common Data Model (CDM). This innovative model standardizes diverse healthcare data into a unified format, thus significantly enhancing the comparability and quality of medical research. Integral to this standardization process are the OMOP vocabularies, which play a pivotal role in ensuring the consistent representation of a wide array of healthcare terminologies.

Within these vocabularies, each medical term, condition, procedure, medication, and other relevant healthcare entities are assigned a unique identifier known as a *concept id*. These *concept ids* are crucial as they provide a consistent reference, linking varied data elements across healthcare databases to a uniform set of standardized concepts. This uniform representation facilitated by *concept ids* is fundamental in achieving interoperability and consistency in data across diverse datasets and systems, making them indispensable tools for effective data integration, analysis, and research within the domain of healthcare informatics.

Establishing a Health Data Space in accordance with the OMOP CDM: Generating a Health Data Space compliant with the OMOP CDM involves mapping diverse sources of data, such as Electronic Health Records (EHRs), Laboratory Information Systems (LIS), Pharmacy Management Systems (PMS), Radiology Information Systems (RIS), and other systems, to the standardized structure of OMOP CDM. This process requires careful transformation of data formats, terminologies, and units to ensure accuracy, consistency, and alignment with OMOP CDM standards.

Integrating AI into a Health Data Space: Integrating AI

into a Health Data Space involves the use of advanced technologies such as Automated Terminology Mapping (ATM) algorithms and Natural Language Processing (NLP) tools to standardize and structure clinical data. ATM algorithms assign standardized OMOP CDM concept ids to structured clinical data from various sources, ensuring seamless integration of hospital data into a standardized framework. Concurrently, NLP tools transform unstructured clinical narratives into structured data by interpreting and categorizing key medical information, aligning it with the OMOP standard, and assigning concept ids to various clinical entities and contexts. This combined approach facilitates the scalable and efficient integration of diverse clinical data into a unified, standardized format, enhancing data interoperability, consistency, and utility for research and clinical decision-making.

2.2 Overview of a Data Space Enablement process

A Data Space in the context of healthcare refers to a comprehensive and interconnected ecosystem where diverse data sources from multiple hospitals and healthcare facilities are integrated and standardized. This integration facilitates seamless data sharing, interoperability, and advanced analytics, ultimately enhancing patient care and research capabilities.

The process of building a Data Space begins with a thorough evaluation of the existing data infrastructure and practices at each participating hospital. This initial phase involves the meticulous cataloging of diverse and often heterogeneous data sources, including Electronic Health Records (EHRs), Laboratory Information Systems (LIS), Pharmacy Management Systems (PMS), Radiology Information Systems (RIS), and other systems. The goal is to transform these varied data sources into a standardized format that ensures data consistency and interoperability across different hospitals.

To achieve this standardization, the Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership Common Data Model (OMOP CDM) is employed as a reference framework. The integration of the OMOP CDM at each hospital is a rigorous and collaborative endeavor [10]. This process requires implementing data transformations (extract, load, transform) from each data source and aligning each record identifier to the identifiers of the OMOP CDM, including the conversion of local terminologies and units into the standardized vocabularies. This systematic approach facilitates a unified view of patient data across multiple hospitals and establishes a robust foundation for comprehensive healthcare research.

In the context of the integration of the OMOP CDM in hospitals, we use AI for further data extraction. We apply multiple techniques such as Automated Terminology Mapping (ATM) to automate the process of mapping local record identifiers to the OMOP CDM standard identifiers and Natural Language Processing (NLP) to extract and structure additional information from clinical notes and other free text sources. For

example, records with the local identifier *weight* in an EHR system will be converted to the OMOP CDM standard identifier *4178502 Body weight measured by the ATM*. The text narratives found in clinical notes and medical charts hold a wealth of clinical insights that are not readily captured in structured databases [7]. We use diverse NLP techniques to recognize, interpret, and categorize key medical information within these texts, transforming it into structured data that aligns with the OMOP CDM. For example, in the sentence "*The patient was diagnosed with diabetes*", the NLP model will extract the entity "*diabetes*" and assign the corresponding concept ID together with its metadata, and the result of the inference will be stored in the *condition* domain of the OMOP CDM.

2.3 Overview of the AI framework

An AI framework constitutes a critical abstraction for the systematic extraction, evaluation, and integration of clinical data from heterogeneous sources into the Health Data Space. This framework ensures that the AI system can manage the complexity and variability inherent in clinical data, while consistently assessing data quality.

Our AI framework is structured into three distinct abstraction levels: Capability, Formula, and Module.

A Capability defines the overall functionality of the AI system, such as identifying mutated genes in texts, and addresses the question, "*What can I do?*" It specifies one or more data sources required to perform the task, the delivery method of the inference, and the target concept IDs it can infer (e.g., BRCA2 gene and storing it in the measurements table).

A Formula outlines the configuration of one or multiple modules required to achieve the goal of the capability, answering the question, "*How do I do it?*" It defines the composition and parameters of the modules and the label concept IDs (e.g., positive, negative, rearranged mutation) it expects as output together with the target concept IDs.

Lastly, a Module is the implementation of an specific technique to perform a specific task. Modules are reusable across different formulas, and improvements in a module impact all formulas that utilize it while maintaining detailed performance metrics at each individual use. This modular approach allows for a high level of specialisation at the formula level while keeping a systematic and generalisable approach to the development of the capabilities. An example of a module is the *Named Entity Recognition (NER)* module, which is a technique used to identify medical entities in clinical texts. The NER module might be used in different formulas to identify different types of medical entities such as genes, proteins, diseases, etc. Those types, would be defined as label concept IDs in the formula.

As shown in Table 1, each capability is designed to capture specific types of clinical information from various data sources, ensuring comprehensive data extraction and integration.

2.3.1 Continuous evaluation and enhancement of the AI framework

Due to the inherently probabilistic nature of AI systems, achieving the expected results requires continuous monitoring and improvement. The AI machinery must be consistently evaluated and refined to adapt to the specific characteristics and nuances of each new cohort or Data Space[11]. The continuous evaluation and enhancement of the capabilities are conducted through a rigorous and systematic process of verification and validation of the AI outputs. This process is inherently iterative and cyclical, which is crucial for several reasons. Firstly, it allows for continuous improvement and refinement of the underlying modules by regularly identifying and addressing issues. Secondly, this iterative approach helps in continuously generating new quality check testing data as well as training data for the underlying systems. By repeatedly cycling through the Diagnose, Act, and Review phases, the system can adapt to new data, incorporate feedback, and enhance its performance over time. This ensures that the AI models remain robust, accurate, and reliable, ultimately leading to better integration and utilization of clinical data. Each of these phases are described in the following sections:

- **Diagnose:** This phase involves the meticulous identification of potential issues or areas for improvement in the inference process of the capabilities. Diagnosis is performed at three hierarchical levels:

The evaluation process is conducted at three hierarchical levels: Capability Level, where we assess if the performance metrics of a specific capability, such as *Gene Mutation Status*, exceed predefined thresholds to ensure expected functionality; Formula Level, where anomalies in capability metrics prompt a more granular evaluation to identify the specific subformula or module responsible for suboptimal performance, allowing for targeted interventions; and Module Level, where a root cause analysis is performed if module metrics do not meet established thresholds, ensuring accurate identification and resolution of underlying issues.

- **Act:** Upon diagnosing a problem, corrective actions are implemented. These actions are executed at the module level, as modules represent the most granular units constituting the formulas and capabilities. Enhancing a module directly influences the formulas and capabilities that incorporate it.

Examples of corrective actions include retraining a model, changing the parameters of a model, optimizing the prompts, adding inclusion or exclusion seed

Capability	Description
<i>Direct Search</i>	Identification of data points explicitly mentioned in clinical notes or structured registries, along with the capture of associated metadata such as patient information, date, visit, and provider details.
<i>Tumor Staging</i>	Extraction of tumor stage using multiple classification systems as recorded in clinical notes such as the stage, TNM or FIGO, and associating this information with the identified tumor.
<i>Scores</i>	Recording of numerical values of indices or scores documented in clinical notes to evaluate various clinical aspects of the patient. e.g. PASI score or the Charlson Comorbidity Index.
<i>Patient State</i>	Capturing the status of a disease as reflected in clinical notes, including states such as relapse, progression, refractory to treatment, or complete response, and associating these states with specific diseases.
<i>Family History</i>	Capturing references to a patient’s family history of specific diseases as documented in clinical notes.
<i>Lesion Progression</i>	Capturing information from clinical notes regarding whether an observed lesion has shown progression.
<i>Treatment Discontinuation</i>	Capturing reasons for drug discontinuation as documented in clinical notes.
<i>Drug Administration</i>	Capturing information on drug administration from clinical notes, including route of administration, dosage frequency, quantity, and strength.
<i>Gene Mutation Status</i>	Capturing mentions of specific gene mutations as documented in clinical notes and structured registries.

Table 1. Overview of the capabilities and their descriptions

terms, adding edge cases to the training and testing data, among others. These actions are meticulously documented and tracked to ensure transparency and accountability.

- **Review:** This phase involves a comprehensive evaluation of the impact of the implemented actions on the process. The evaluation is conducted at the capability level, where the changes are ultimately manifested. Reviewing entails verifying whether the improvements in the modules have positively influenced the capability to address the original issue. It is crucial to measure progress through aggregated metrics from both the modules and the formulas to ascertain if the actions have achieved the desired effect.

The continuous evaluation and improvement process is designed to be rigorous and systematic, ensuring that the capabilities are in a state of perpetual enhancement. By iteratively refining the modules based on performance metrics and feedback from the verification and validation processes, we ensure that the AI framework remains robust, accurate, and reliable. This iterative approach not only enhances the quality of the AI outputs but also establishes rigorous quality checks, fostering a culture of continuous improvement and excellence.

2.4 AI capability evaluated in this study

For this study, we will focus on the *Direct Search* capability, which is a technique used to identify individual datapoints that are explicitly mentioned in the clinical notes or available in the structured data. It’s composed of two formulas: *Explicit Mention Formula* and *Automated Mapping Formula*. This capability is used in all clinical notes available in the EHRs as well as structured data records. The results of this capability are stored back in the OMOP CDM, in the tables of the domain

of the concept id that is being inferred, associated with the patient identifier, the date of the record and the provider; no other related data is stored.

2.4.1 Automated Mapping Formula

The OMOP CDM enables the standardization of clinical data to facilitate systematic research across multiple hospitals. However, this process often involves manual mapping of internal hospital codes to standard concept ids, which is time-consuming and labor-intensive.

The goal of this *formula* is that given as input a set of tabular data, with an *id* that refers to a class of data (e.g. *data_id* [weight]) that does not have a direct mapping to an standardized terminology, provide the equivalent code in the OMOP CDM, such as the *concept_id* 4178502 *Measured body weight*.

As shown in Figure 1, the main goal of automating OMOP mapping is to minimize the manual effort needed to assign standard codes to hospital data. This is achieved through the use of a semantic search with embeddings, which transform text descriptions and metadata into numerical vectors with semantics that capture the underlying meaning[12]. These vectors are then used to compute similarities between descriptions and other metadata, automating the identification of appropriate standard concept ids.

2.4.2 Explicit Mention Formula

This formula is used to identify datapoints that are explicitly mentioned in the clinical notes. It’s composed of three modules: *Named Entity Recognition (NER)*, *Named Entity Linking (NEL)*, and *Entity Metadata Extraction (EME)*. Each of these modules are used to extract the data from the clinical notes or to obtain the necessary metadata to correctly transform it into a concept id.

ID	patient_id	data_id	date	value	unit	visit
643	243	weight	2021-10-12	190	lbs	367
2891	243	weight	2021-11-21	170	lbs	458

Non-standard codification

...	person_id	observation_concept_id	observation_date	value_as_number	...
...	243	3025315	2021-10-12	86.18	...

OMOP CDM
Observation

Figure 1. A visual representation of the Mapping formula

noteID	person_id	date	value	visit
1	243	2021-10-12	follow up. 02-17-2015 usual f/up Follow-Up: Consultation on pain left arm since yesterday. [The smorning pain persists. Had similar pain whn had AMI. Has taken nitrostat without improvement. Request of ECG	367

Data stored in free-text format

...	person_id	procedure_concept_id	procedure_date	visit_occurrence_id	...
...	243	4115169	2021-10-12	896	...

OMOP CDM
Procedure Occurrence

Figure 2. A visual representation of the Explicit Mention formula

• **Named Entity Recognition (NER) Module:**

The NER module identifies a wide range of medical entities and their domains (conditions, procedures, medications, etc.) from clinical narratives.

Each entity is labeled with its domain and is associated with the position of where it starts and ends in the text. For example, in the sentence *"The patient was diagnosed with diabetes"* if *"diabetes"* is recognized as a disorder entity, the model will not only label it as a disease but also provide indices indicating where the word *"diabetes"* starts and ends in the sentence.

• **Named Entity Linking (NEL) Module:**

This module links each identified entity in the NER Module to a specific OMOP CDM concept id, converting raw data into an standardized identifier that can be stored in the OMOP CDM. Following the previous example, the entity *"diabetes"* would be assigned with the

201820: *"Diabetes Mellitus"* concept id, providing a unique identifier that corresponds to an existing record in a structured database.

• **Entity Metadata Extraction (EME) Module:**

This module extracts important metadata from each entity (affirmation or negation, temporal context, certainty, subject, etc.). In the example of *"The patient was diagnosed with diabetes"*, the module will extract the metadata *"affirmation"*, *"temporal context"* as *past*, *"subject"* as *patient*, as the sentence is asserting that the patient had been diagnosed with diabetes in the past and it refers to the patient and not to another individual such as a sibling or a parent.

3. Materials

The primary materials for this study encompass two main components: 10 multi-centric cohorts and the performance metrics of the AI capabilities employed for the enhancement of Health Data Spaces for those cohorts. The performance metrics were collected from concepts utilized in the data mediation process of the 10 cohorts across 10 Data Spaces in Europe. For this study, a total of 550 concept IDs were selected to conduct a comprehensive comparative performance analysis across multiple sites and cohorts, aimed at evaluating the generalizability of the AI capabilities.

3.1 Data Spaces

This study utilized 10 clinical databases from hospitals located across Europe, each converted into the OMOP CDM. These datasets encompassed diverse real-world clinical data, including clinical notes, radiology reports, pathology reports, and additional unstructured data relevant to patient care. The OMOP CDM was chosen to standardize data integration and facilitate cross-institutional comparisons.

3.2 Cohorts

We employed 10 distinct cohorts from previously conducted real-world studies. These cohorts, previously subjected to verification and validation through the framework, represent a diverse range of clinical conditions and were used as benchmarks for evaluating the performance of the AI capabilities.

To comprehensively evaluate the utility of AI-driven clinical data extraction, we conducted a comparative analysis across all 10 distinct cohorts. Each cohort was assessed twice: once using only previously available data, and again incorporating AI-generated data points into the analysis. This within-cohort comparison allowed us to isolate the effects of AI-driven data augmentation on clinical data extraction performance, thereby providing a comprehensive understanding of the added value that AI can bring to this process. By analyzing each cohort under both conditions, we were able to generate 20 unique datasets, which collectively enabled us to quantify the im-

pact of AI-driven data enhancement on our ability to extract meaningful clinical insights from real-world data.

We defined previously available data as data in the original source of data that was already mapped into a terminology such as ICD-10, LOINC, SNOMED CT, etc as this can be easily tracked in the OMOP CDM as `source_value` in all the tables.

The therapeutic areas of the cohorts include Multiple Sclerosis, Chronic Urticaria, Psoriasis, Ulcerative Colitis, Multiple Myeloma, Acute Myeloid Leukemia, Prostate Cancer, Endometrial Cancer, Hypophosphatemia, and Alport Syndrome.

3.3 Performance metrics

The performance metrics for the cohorts encompass several dimensions. Firstly, verification metrics pertain to the accuracy of the concepts extracted by the AI capabilities within each cohort. Secondly, validation metrics evaluate both the extracted concepts and the cohorts themselves, ensuring the reliability and consistency of the AI-generated data. Additionally, performance metrics of the annotators, who are responsible for verifying the AI-extracted concepts, are also considered.

3.3.1 Verification metrics of the capabilities

We perform a verification process of the inferred data by the capabilities to ensure that the data is correct prior to its integration into the OMOP CDM. This is a physician-led process where they review a data sample to ensure its accuracy. Physicians are trained how to evaluate the outputs of the capabilities in the context of clinical information. These annotators apply their medical expertise and understanding of outputs of the capabilities to review and assess the accuracy and clinical relevance of the identified terms from the source of data. The evaluation process consists of the following steps:

1. **Evaluation of True Positives (TP) and False Positives (FP):** Physicians perform a remote source data verification (rSDV) process over a significant sample for each concept id in each Hospital where the a *capability* is used. Annotators identify the correctness of the capability, checking the concept id assignment and other context. Each annotation is cross-verified by at least two annotators to calculate a disagreement score. To conduct the evaluation, each annotator is presented with the original data alongside the output generated by the *capability*, as illustrated in Figure 3. The annotator's task involves a critical assessment of whether the *module's* inference aligns accurately with the expected data. In cases where the inference is deemed incorrect, the annotator provides specific feedback identifying the *modules* responsible for the error. This process results in the classification of TP for all correctly functioning *modules* and FP for any *module* that contributed to an erroneous inference.

2. **Evaluation of True Negatives (TN):** In the context of the *capabilities*, evaluating all TN is unfeasible due to the nature of these tasks. The vast amount of tabular data or text in clinical records inherently contains an infinite number of potential TNs — entities that are correctly not identified or linked by the *capability*. Since *capabilities* are designed to identify specific cases, the majority of the source data is, by default, not relevant to the task and thus forms a vast pool of TNs.

Randomly during the rSDV process, a sample of negative datapoints are included in the process to assert their TN nature or consider them FN. The TN datapoint will be a negative for the *capability* and one or more of the modules that are part of the *capability* such as the NEL or contexts of the entity. For example, a datapoint that might have been identified as *"Not referring to the patient"*, is included in the review process, so that *"the patient refers that her mother had breast cancer at a young age"*, while reviewing *"breast cancer"*, the annotator should review it as a wrong inference and tick the *"Does not refer to patient"* option as it can be seen in the Figure 3.

3. **Evaluation of False Negatives (FN):** Identifying False Negatives—instances where the AI system fails to detect relevant clinical information—is challenging due to their rarity in vast datasets of unannotated clinical records. Random sampling is ineffective because these missed detections are infrequent and randomly reviewing data is unlikely to uncover them. Moreover, manually examining all clinical notes is impractical given the enormous volume of data and the resources required.

To address this, we implement a semantic similarity search approach[13]. This method involves generating *query vectors* from data points that the system has correctly identified as relevant. These vectors capture the semantic characteristics of known positive cases. We then compare these query vectors against the entire dataset to find similar but previously unrecognized instances—potential False Negatives. By focusing on data points that are semantically similar to confirmed positives, we increase the likelihood of identifying cases the AI may have missed.

Once these potential False Negatives are identified, they undergo a remote Source Data Verification (rSDV) process conducted by a physician. The physician reviews the original clinical data associated with these cases to confirm whether they are indeed relevant instances that the AI system failed to detect. This targeted validation enables us to efficiently identify and correct False Negatives, thereby enhancing the performance and reliability of the AI capabilities.

Figure 3. Example of a rSDV process, a clinical note and the inference are shown together for its evaluation.

4. **Computation of the performance metrics:** The effectiveness of the *modules* is measured using performance metrics from the confusion matrix. This includes checking if entities have the correct domain, ID, and EME label. Metrics are provided for both individual *modules* and the overall *capability*. The key performance metrics are: Precision (also known as Positive Predictive Value), Recall (also known as Sensitivity) and F1-Score.

3.3.2 Sample size determination for the verification metrics

Our *capability* evaluation adopts a Bayesian statistical framework to estimate the required sample size per hospital, cohort and concept id for evaluating the *modules*.

1. **Defining prior distribution** If for the concept id being evaluated we have no prior data from other Data Spaces, we initiate our analysis by defining a prior distribution for the proportion of correctly identified entities, p , using a Beta distribution. The Beta distribution is chosen for its conjugacy with the binomial *module* and its flexibility in representing different states of prior knowledge. In the absence of prior data, we utilize a uniform prior, Beta(1, 1), to reflect a state of complete uncertainty.
2. **Setting performance criteria** Our performance criteria are set as follows:
 - Level of Confidence: 95%

- Margin of Error: 5%

These parameters ensure that the true proportion of correctly identified entities falls within our calculated interval with a high degree of certainty.

3. **Calculation of the sample size** We employ an iterative method to calculate the minimum sample size required to achieve our specified margin of error within the desired confidence level. The sample size is determined by the point at which the width of the 95% credible interval of p falls below the predefined margin of error.
4. **Stopping rule** A stopping rule is implemented based on the precision of our estimates. The annotation process is halted when the width of the 95% credible interval for p is less than or equal to 10% of p . This rule ensures that the precision of the estimate is proportionate to the estimate itself, optimizing the balance between accuracy and annotation effort.

3.3.3 Validation metrics of the data

To systematically evaluate the quality of data of a capability, cohort and a Data Space, we perform a series of predefined checks across various data quality dimensions, including completeness, conformance, and plausibility. We establish a repeatable and continuously improvable process to evaluate the data quality, providing a Level 3 Data Quality Assessment (DQA) as defined per Callahan et al.[14].

The checks are organized according to the Kahn Framework for harmonized data quality assessment[15], which provides a structured approach for assessing data quality for the secondary use of clinical data. The Kahn Framework categorizes data quality assessment into different dimensions and contexts, offering a comprehensive system for evaluating the reliability and usability of data from health care systems.

The goal of this analysis is to evaluate improvements in data quality dimensions attributable to AI-generated data points. The dimensions assessed were:

- **Completeness:** Measure that all necessary data elements are present and accounted for.
- **Conformance:** Measure the proportion of data points that conform to the expected format and structure. This includes verifying that data fields adhere to predefined formats, such as date formats, numerical ranges, and categorical values. Conformance checks ensure that the data follows the required standards and formats, making it easier to integrate and analyze.
- **Plausibility:** Measure the proportion of data points that are plausible and consistent with the known information. This includes checks for atemporal plausibility, such as ensuring that values fall within realistic ranges (e.g., no negative ages), and temporal plausibility, such as ensuring that event dates are logically consistent (e.g., a diagnosis date should not precede a birth date). Plausibility checks help in identifying data that is believable and logically consistent.

Qualitative Evaluation In addition to the systematic checks, a qualitative clinical evaluation is performed for the cohorts. This involves analyzing clinical validity over the resulting datasets. This step is crucial for validating the overall integrity and coherence of the data with the clinical context.

3.3.4 Evaluation of the clinical annotators

The monitoring of the performance of the physicians participating in the rSDV process is essential to ensure the accuracy of the annotations used to evaluate the performance of the *capabilities*. To this end, we implemented a real-time algorithm designed to evaluate and ensure the accuracy of annotations through an inter-annotator agreement score. Two different clinical annotators are initially assigned to perform the same annotations task independently. The system distributes the task randomly among annotators and monitors for identical responses. Once two annotators provide matching annotations, these are marked as correct, and the task distribution ceases. In instances where annotations differ, the target is incrementally increased by one, and the task is reassigned to a different annotator. This cycle repeats until an agreement is reached or the count of annotations meets the threshold

of seven annotations. This approach is refined by additional measures:

- Annotators with a disagreement score below 85% after three weeks and subsequent feedback are subject to reconsideration, ensuring a high standard of data accuracy. We also track True Negative (TN) data points that are annotated as such, which aids in the comprehensive evaluation of the annotation quality.
- Golden annotators, physicians with a higher level of expertise in the annotations task and a thorough understanding of the data, are used to continuously annotate samples of the data and the performance of all clinical annotators is evaluated against the golden annotators in a continuous basis, providing an additional benchmark for the quality of the annotations. This is done by calculating the Cohen's Kappa score between the golden annotator and the clinical annotators. This ensures that the clinical annotators are meeting the required standard and are able to keep their performance. This evaluation is conducted additionally to the inter-annotator agreement score.
- Time per Task (TPT) is monitored, noting the minimum and maximum time spent on tasks, which provides insights into the efficiency and engagement levels of the annotators.

These combined strategies enhance the overall efficiency and accuracy of the annotation process, which is crucial for the reliability of *capabilities* outputs in clinical applications.

4. Methods

Our methodological approach focuses on the evaluation of the impact of AI-generated data points on clinical cohort studies and the generalizability of the AI capabilities across different cohorts and centers.

Evaluating cohorts with and without AI-generated data points allows us to assess the added value of AI in clinical data extraction. This analysis quantifies improvements in data completeness, accuracy, and overall quality of downstream results. By comparing clinical outcomes, statistical significance, effect sizes, and model performance metrics, we demonstrate how AI-derived data enhances dataset richness and utility. This approach validates the AI processes and highlights their significance in uncovering insights that structured data alone might miss, proving the value of AI integration in clinical research.

Understanding the generalizability of our AI capabilities is crucial for ensuring that the models we develop are applicable across diverse clinical settings and patient populations. Quantitative performance metrics such as accuracy and F1-score

Figure 4. Qualitative check of the resulting data

serve as empirical evidence of this generalizability. Consistent and robust performance metrics across different cohorts and centers indicate that our AI models capture underlying patterns common across various clinical environments, rather than being tailored to specific datasets. Minimal variability of these metrics across diverse datasets demonstrates that the models handle the inherent heterogeneity of real-world clinical data, ensuring that the AI-generated data points are reliable for use in clinical research and practice across various data sources.

Finally, we evaluate the inter-rater reliability of the annotation process to ensure that the metrics used to evaluate the AI capabilities are consistent and reliable.

4.1 Quantitative analysis of the impact of AI-generated data points in the cohorts

To assess the value of the use of AI in clinical data extraction, we conducted a comparative analysis of the same cohorts using only previously available data and comparing it to the same cohorts but adding the results of the AI-generated data points to it.

4.1.1 Comparative analysis of the downstream outcomes

The goal of this analysis is to assess how the inclusion of AI-generated data points affects the results of downstream

analyses or studies. For each cohort, a primary outcome was identified based on clinical relevance. The analysis involved comparing the primary outcome before and after the inclusion of AI generated data points. This comparison was performed using paired statistical tests to evaluate the significance of any observed differences. Additionally, effect sizes were calculated to quantify the magnitude of these differences.

Method:

- **Statistical significance testing:** Employ paired statistical tests appropriate for the data type and distribution (e.g., paired *t* test for continuous variables, McNemar’s test for categorical variables) to determine if observed differences between datasets are statistically significant.
- **Effect size calculation:** Compute effect sizes to quantify the magnitude of differences in outcomes between the two datasets. Cohen’s *d* measures the effect size by quantifying the magnitude of the difference between two groups, assessing the impact of AI integration on clinical outcomes. Odds Ratio compares the odds of an event occurring in one group to the odds of it occurring in another group, evaluating the likelihood of positive clinical outcomes before and after AI integration.

4.1.2 Data Quality Assessment

To demonstrate that the inclusion of AI-generated data points does not degrade data quality, we conducted a non-inferiority analysis comparing the validation metrics before and after the integration of AI-generated data. The objective was to statistically confirm that the data quality post-integration is not inferior to the pre-integration data quality within a predefined acceptable margin.

the proportion of missing values before and after adding AI-generated data. This involves identifying fields with missing values and comparing the percentage of missing data in the original dataset versus the dataset enhanced with AI-generated data points. Completeness ensures w

4.1.3 Assessment of the volume and diversity of data

The goal of this analysis is to quantify and understand the amount of new information added to the cohorts, being previously not available concept IDs and data points, introduced by AI capabilities.

Method:

- **Volume of data:** Quantify the number of unique data points identified by the AI algorithms and perform a comparative analysis with the number of unique data points in the original dataset. This quantification serves as an indicator of the novel information introduced by the AI. Additionally, enumerate the unique concept IDs identified by the AI algorithms and compare these to the unique concept IDs present in the original dataset. This enumeration provides a metric for assessing the extent of new information introduced by the AI.
- **Diversity of data:** Calculate the diversity of concept identifiers and the data points, being previously not available in the dataset, introduced by AI. This involves analyzing the distribution of concept identifiers across different centers to understand the extent of diversity in the AI-generated data. Measuring diversity with an index allows us to quantitatively compare the new unique concept IDs added in each center and cohort, providing a standardized metric to assess the impact of AI on data enrichment. To do so, we computed the Margalef's index of diversity[16] for each center of the cohort. This index is calculated as:

$$\text{Margalef's Index} = \frac{S - 1}{\ln N} \quad (1)$$

where S is the number of unique concept IDs and N is the total number of data points in the cohort and center. A higher index value indicates a higher diversity of data points.

This index is calculated for the original dataset and for the AI-enhanced dataset. The difference between

the two indices is used to quantify the increase in the diversity of data points introduced by AI.

4.1.4 Individual Patient Data Completeness and Temporal Coverage

To comprehensively evaluate the impact of AI-generated data points on the completeness and temporal coverage at the individual patient level, we adopt a patient-centric approach on the evaluation of the completeness of data per clinical domain and temporal coverage. The goal of this analysis is to determine the extent to which AI-generated data points enhance the completeness and temporal coverage of individual patient records.

Method:

- **Completeness of Patient Data per Domain: Completeness Calculation:** Calculate the proportion of added concept IDs for each domain before and after adding AI-generated data points. This involves identifying fields with added concept IDs and comparing the percentage of added data in the AI-enhanced dataset versus the original dataset. We used paired statistical tests, such as the Wilcoxon signed-rank test, to compare the completeness of data per domain before and after the inclusion of AI-generated data points. This will help determine if there are statistically significant improvements in data completeness.
- **Temporal Coverage of Patient Data:**
 - **Event Timeline Construction:** For each patient, construct timelines of recorded clinical events from both the original and AI-enhanced datasets, noting the dates and sequence of each event.
 - **Temporal Span Analysis:** Calculate the temporal span for each patient by measuring the interval between the earliest and latest recorded events in both datasets. This will provide insights into the temporal coverage of patient data.
 - **Event Density Calculation:** Determine the average number of events per unit time (e.g., per month or year) for each patient to assess the granularity of temporal data coverage.
 - **Gap Analysis:** Calculate the number of gaps in the timeline of clinical events for each patient. A gap is defined as a period without any recorded events in both datasets. This will help identify periods where AI-generated data enhances patient profiles.
 - **Statistical Comparison:** Use paired statistical tests, such as the Wilcoxon signed-rank test or paired t-test, to evaluate differences in temporal spans and event

densities between the original and AI-enhanced datasets. This will help identify any significant improvements in temporal coverage.

4.2 Consistency of the AI capability evaluation metrics across Data Spaces and cohorts

Ensuring the generalizability and robustness of AI-generated data points is critical when deploying AI models across diverse clinical settings. In this study, we evaluated the performance of our AI capability *Direct Search* across 10 Data Spaces, using the F1-score as the primary evaluation metric. To thoroughly assess the consistency, variability, and reliability of the AI model's performance, we employed a suite of complementary statistical analyses, each offering unique insights into different aspects of the capability's performance.

First, we used the *Intraclass Correlation Coefficient (ICC)* to assess the *consistency* of the F1 scores across Data Spaces. The ICC is particularly useful when analyzing the agreement or consistency of measurements across groups. A high ICC would indicate that the AI model's performance is stable and consistent across different centers or cohorts, suggesting that external factors (such as variations in data sources or patient populations) have minimal impact on model behavior. Conversely, a low ICC would suggest that the model's performance is more variable, potentially highlighting issues with generalizability.

The *Coefficient of Variation (CV)* was employed to measure the *relative variability* of F1 scores. The CV normalizes the standard deviation relative to the mean, providing insight into the extent of performance variability compared to the average performance. A low CV indicates stable performance, with minimal deviation from the average, while a high CV suggests greater variability in the model's effectiveness. This analysis helps quantify how much the model's performance fluctuates relative to the typical F1 score across different settings.

We then applied *Levene's Test* to evaluate whether the *variance* in F1 scores differed significantly between Data Spaces. Levene's Test is robust against deviations from normality and is particularly useful in assessing whether certain centers exhibit higher or lower variability in performance compared to others. This analysis helps identify whether specific Data Spaces or cohorts present unique challenges for the AI model, which might manifest as greater inconsistency in performance.

Next, we fitted a *Mixed-Effects Model* to account for *both fixed and random effects* in the data. The mixed-effects model allowed us to separate the overall trends (fixed effects) from center-specific variations (random effects), providing a more nuanced understanding of the factors influencing the model's performance. This approach was essential for identifying whether certain predictors (such as cohort or concept) systematically affected performance, while also accounting for the variability introduced by different centers. The random-effects

component helped isolate whether variations in performance were due to center-specific factors or random fluctuations.

Finally, we conducted a *random-effects meta-analysis* to synthesize the F1 scores across centers. This method was critical in obtaining a more generalized estimate of the model's performance by combining the results from multiple Data Spaces. Unlike a traditional analysis, a random-effects meta-analysis accounts for both within-center and between-center variability, allowing for generalization to a broader population of clinical settings. This aggregation also enhanced statistical power, providing a more precise overall estimate of the model's effectiveness while acknowledging that performance may vary randomly between centers.

By integrating these analyses, we were able to conduct a comprehensive evaluation of the AI model's performance across a wide range of clinical environments. Together, these methods allowed us to assess not only the consistency and reliability of the AI model across different centers but also the factors contributing to variability and the model's potential for generalizability across broader healthcare settings.

4.2.1 Intraclass Correlation Coefficient (ICC)

The Intraclass Correlation Coefficient (ICC) quantifies the degree of similarity of measurements within groups and is particularly useful for assessing the reliability and consistency of measurements across different categories. In our study, the ICC helps determine how consistently the AI model performs across different Data Spaces and cohorts.

A low ICC value (close to 0) indicates that the variability in F1-scores is primarily due to differences within Data Spaces rather than between them. This suggests that the AI model performs consistently across various clinical settings and generalizes well across diverse clinical environments. Conversely, a high ICC value (close to 1) indicates significant variability attributable to differences between Data Spaces, meaning that the model's performance varies across Data Spaces and cohorts, indicating potential issues with the model's generalizability.

The steps involved in calculating the ICC are as follows:

1. Collect F1-scores for each concept from each Data Space and cohort for the AI capability *Direct Search*.
2. Decompose the total variance observed in the F1-scores into two components:
 - *Between-Data Space variance* ($\sigma_{\text{between}}^2$): Variability in F1-scores due to differences between Data Spaces.
 - *Within-Data Space variance* (σ_{within}^2): Variability in F1-scores within the same Data Space and across cohorts.

3. Calculate the ICC using the formula:

$$ICC = \frac{\sigma_{\text{between}}^2}{\sigma_{\text{between}}^2 + \sigma_{\text{within}}^2} \quad (2)$$

4.2.2 Coefficient of Variation (CV)

The Coefficient of Variation (CV) is a standardized measure of the dispersion. In the context of this study, the CV is particularly useful for comparing the degree of variation in AI model performance across different Data Spaces. By evaluating the CV of F1-scores, we can assess how consistently the AI model performs across various clinical settings. A low CV indicates that the model’s performance is stable and consistent, while a high CV suggests significant variability, which may point to issues with the model’s generalizability or stability in different environments.

$$CV = \frac{\sigma}{\mu} \times 100\% \quad (3)$$

where σ is the standard deviation and μ is the mean of the F1-scores.

Given that each concept is evaluated independently in every Data Space, we can compute the CV of the same concept across multiple Data Spaces. To evaluate the consistency of the AI model’s performance, we calculated the CV of the F1-scores across various Data Spaces. The steps involved in calculating the CV are as follows:

1. Collect F1-scores for each concept from each Data Space and cohort for the AI capability *Direct Search*.
2. Calculate the standard deviation of the F1-scores for each concept across the Data Spaces.
3. Determine the CV by dividing the standard deviation by the mean and multiplying by 100 to express it as a percentage.

With the Coefficient of Variation (CV) calculated for 550 concepts, as well as globally for all concepts, the next steps involve analyzing and interpreting these values to gain insights into the consistency and reliability of the AI model’s performance across different Data Spaces. A *low CV* indicates that the AI model’s performance for a concept is consistent across different Data Spaces, suggesting good generalizability. A *high CV* suggests significant variability in performance, which might indicate issues with the model’s stability or generalizability for that concept.

4.2.3 Levene’s Test

Levene’s Test is a statistical method used to assess the equality of variances across multiple groups. Unlike traditional tests for homogeneity of variances, such as Bartlett’s Test, Levene’s Test is more robust to deviations from normality, making it particularly useful in real-world data settings where

the assumption of normal distribution might not hold. This test is especially relevant when there are suspicions that the variances across groups (in this case, centers) are not equal, which can indicate that certain groups have greater or lesser variability in performance metrics like F1 scores.

In this study, Levene’s Test was applied to determine whether the *variability in F1 scores across different centers* is consistent or if certain centers exhibit systematically higher or lower variances. This analysis helps identify whether some centers are more consistent in their performance, while others experience more fluctuation, potentially due to factors like data quality, annotation practices, or patient population differences.

Levene’s Test is particularly useful in this analysis because it helps detect whether certain centers exhibit disproportionately high or low variability in their F1 scores, which could reflect underlying differences in data reliability, annotation standards, or model performance. Identifying such variability is important for understanding whether the AI model performs consistently across different clinical settings or if some centers pose unique challenges that contribute to greater fluctuation in performance.

4.2.4 Quantifying Center Variability in AI Performance via Bayesian Hierarchical Modeling

To account for potential variability in the AI model’s performance across centers, we employed a *Bayesian hierarchical model* with a *Beta likelihood*. This type of model is particularly well-suited for hierarchical or clustered data structures, where observations within the same group (in this case, centers) may not be independent of one another. The Bayesian hierarchical model allowed us to account for both *fixed effects* (systematic differences across cohorts) and *random effects* (group-specific variations at the center level).

The F1 score, bounded between 0 and 1, was modeled using a Beta distribution:

$$F1 \text{ score}_i \sim \text{Beta}(\alpha_i, \beta_i)$$

where α_i and β_i are the shape parameters of the Beta distribution, parameterized by the mean μ_i and precision ϕ . The mean F1 score μ_i was modeled as a function of both fixed and random effects:

$$\log \left(\frac{\mu_i}{1 - \mu_i} \right) = \gamma_0 + \gamma_{\text{cohort}} + b_{\text{center}}[j]$$

where γ_0 represents the *global intercept*, γ_{cohort} represents the *fixed effect* associated with cohort i , and $b_{\text{center}}[j]$ represents the *random intercept* for center j .

The random intercept $b_{\text{center}}[j]$ was modeled as:

$$b_{\text{center}}[j] \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_{\text{center}}^2)$$

where σ_{center} represents the standard deviation of the center-specific effects, allowing each center to have its own baseline F1 score.

Likelihood and Priors

Given the bounded nature of the F1 scores, a Beta distribution was chosen to model the likelihood, ensuring that the predictions remained within the $[0,1]$ interval. The likelihood for the F1 score was therefore:

$$\text{F1 score}_i \sim \text{Beta}(\mu_i \cdot \phi, (1 - \mu_i) \cdot \phi)$$

where μ_i is the mean of the F1 score and ϕ is a precision parameter governing the variance of the distribution. A logit link function was used to map the mean μ_i from the real line to the $[0,1]$ interval.

Non-informative or weakly informative priors were specified for the global intercept γ_0 , the cohort-level fixed effects γ_{cohort} , and the center-level random effects $b_{\text{center}[j]}$. Specifically:

$$\gamma_0 \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 5)$$

$$\gamma_{\text{cohort}} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 5)$$

$$\sigma_{\text{center}} \sim \text{HalfNormal}(1)$$

The precision parameter ϕ was given a weakly informative prior to allow flexibility in the variance:

$$\phi \sim \text{Gamma}(2, 0.1)$$

Inference and Posterior Predictive Checks

The model was fit using Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) sampling via the No-U-Turn Sampler (NUTS), implemented in PyMC 4. Posterior samples were drawn using 2,000 iterations, with an additional 1,000 iterations for warm-up. The posterior distributions of the parameters were evaluated for convergence using trace plots and the Gelman-Rubin statistic.

To assess the fit of the model, we conducted posterior predictive checks (PPCs), comparing the simulated F1 scores from the posterior predictive distribution to the observed F1 scores. This allowed us to evaluate how well the model captured the key patterns and variability in the data, including both cohort-level and center-level effects.

4.2.5 Meta-Analysis of Center Performance

A random-effects meta-analysis was conducted to synthesize the F1-scores across centers, accounting for both within-center variability and random between-center differences. This approach assumes that the performance of the AI model may vary randomly across centers due to inherent center-specific factors (e.g., differences in data quality, annotation practices, or patient demographics). The methodology for the meta-analysis is outlined as follows:

1. Collect F1-scores from each center, treating the centers as random samples from a broader population of potential clinical settings.
2. Calculate the within-center variance for each center, which captures the variability in F1-scores specific to each center.
3. Apply inverse-variance weighting, where centers with lower within-center variance contribute more to the overall estimate, ensuring that centers with more reliable estimates are weighted accordingly.
4. Use a random-effects model to combine the F1-scores, accounting for between-center variability. This model assumes that differences between centers are random and allows the overall estimate of performance to generalize to other centers not included in the analysis.
5. Assess the heterogeneity among centers, using statistics such as I^2 to quantify the proportion of total variability attributable to between-center differences. This measures how much of the variability in F1-scores is due to differences across centers versus within centers.

The random-effects model was chosen to account for the possibility that center-specific factors could cause variability in performance, allowing for more generalizable conclusions about the AI model's effectiveness across diverse clinical settings. High heterogeneity (I^2) would indicate significant between-center differences, while low heterogeneity suggests that the variability in performance is mostly driven by within-center factors.

4.3 Inter-rater Reliability Analysis

To ensure the robustness and consistency of our AI-driven data extraction and integration process, we conducted a comprehensive inter-rater reliability analysis. This analysis is crucial for evaluating the performance of physician performing the annotation in the verification process, which serves as a critical quality control measure for our AI capabilities.

4.3.1 Fleiss' Kappa

We employed Fleiss' Kappa, a statistical measure designed to assess the reliability of agreement between multiple raters when evaluating categorical data. This choice aligns with our verification process, which involves categorizing AI outputs into predefined classes (e.g., correct identification, incorrect identification, or ambiguous cases).

The Fleiss' Kappa calculation process involves the following steps:

1. Definition of evaluation categories based on our verification criteria.
2. Collection of rater assignments for each data point across all evaluators.
3. Construction of a matrix representing items and rater decisions.
4. Calculation of observed agreement among raters.

5. Estimation of expected agreement under the assumption of chance.
6. Computation of the Fleiss' Kappa coefficient using the formula:

$$\kappa = \frac{P_o - P_e}{1 - P_e} \quad (4)$$

where P_o represents the observed agreement and P_e the expected agreement by chance.

We applied this methodology across our diverse cohorts and participating centers, allowing us to:

- Assess the consistency of evaluator performance across different clinical contexts and data sources.
- Identify potential discrepancies or biases in the evaluation process that might affect the reliability of our AI-generated data points.
- Provide a quantitative measure of the reliability of our human-in-the-loop verification process.

By ensuring high inter-rater reliability, we strengthen the credibility of our AI-enhanced data extraction and integration methodology, supporting the overall goal of creating robust, standardized clinical data repositories for advanced healthcare analytics and research.

4.3.2 Time per Task (TPT) Analysis

The Time per Task (TPT) metric is used to assess the efficiency and engagement levels of annotators. To evaluate and analyze this metric, we employ the following methods:

1. **TPT Calculation:** For each annotator, calculate the TPT as:

$$TPT = \frac{\text{Total time spent on tasks}}{\text{Number of tasks completed}} \quad (5)$$

2. **Descriptive Statistics:** Compute mean, median, standard deviation, and interquartile range of TPT across all annotators.
3. **Distribution Analysis:**
 - Generate histograms and box plots to visualize TPT distribution.
 - Perform Shapiro-Wilk test to assess normality of TPT distribution.
4. **Outlier Detection:** Use Tukey's method ($1.5 * IQR$ rule) to identify potential outliers in TPT.
5. **Trend Analysis:**
 - Plot TPT over time to detect any learning effects or fatigue.
 - Perform linear regression to quantify trends.
6. **Comparative Analysis:**
 - Conduct one-way ANOVA or Kruskal-Wallis test (depending on normality) to compare TPT across different annotator groups or task types.

- Perform post-hoc tests (e.g., Tukey's HSD) for pairwise comparisons if significant differences are found.

7. **Correlation Analysis:** Calculate Pearson's or Spearman's correlation coefficient between TPT and other metrics (e.g., accuracy, agreement scores) to assess potential relationships.
8. **Efficiency Thresholds:** Establish TPT thresholds based on expert consensus or historical data to categorize annotators as high, medium, or low efficiency.
9. **Statistical Process Control:** Implement control charts (e.g., Individual-Moving Range charts) to monitor TPT stability over time and detect any special cause variations.

This comprehensive analysis of TPT will provide insights into annotator efficiency, identify potential areas for improvement in the annotation process, and help establish benchmarks for future annotation tasks.

4.3.3 Agreement Score with the Golden Annotators

The Agreement Score with the Golden Annotators is calculated to assess the agreement between the annotators and the golden annotators. The Agreement Score is defined as the percentage of tasks that the annotators agree on. The steps involved in calculating the Agreement Score are as follows:

1. Collect the annotations from the annotators and the golden annotators.
2. Compare the annotations from the annotators and the golden annotators.
3. Calculate the Agreement Score by dividing the number of tasks that the annotators agree on by the total number of tasks.

5. Discussion

The implementation of AI pipelines within the OMOP Common Data Model (CDM) framework has demonstrated significant advancements in clinical data management. The study's findings underscore the efficacy of NLP and ATM in enhancing the accuracy and comprehensiveness of clinical data extraction and mapping processes.

- **Improved Data Accuracy and Utility:** The integration of NLP and ATM technologies has markedly improved the precision of data captured from unstructured clinical narratives and tabular data. The verification process, led by experienced physicians, confirmed that the models accurately identified and classified clinical entities, ensuring high-fidelity data representation. This enhancement is crucial for subsequent clinical research and patient care applications.
- **Streamlined Data Standardization:** Automating the mapping of internal hospital codes to OMOP CDM con-

cept IDs has significantly reduced the manual effort and time required for data standardization. This automation has led to a more efficient integration of diverse clinical data sources, enhancing interoperability and enabling large-scale analytics across multiple hospitals.

- **Scalability and Generalizability:** The methodologies employed in this study, particularly the use of advanced AI techniques for data extraction and validation, are highly scalable and can be generalized to different healthcare settings and data sources such as imaging and omics. This scalability is critical for expanding the adoption of standardized data models across various institutions, fostering a more unified and comprehensive health data ecosystem.

5.1 Limitations

Despite the promising results, the study also encountered several limitations that should be considered:

- **Dependence on High-Quality Annotations:** The accuracy of the NLP models heavily relies on the quality of the annotations provided by the clinical experts. Variability in annotator expertise and agreement can introduce biases, potentially affecting the overall reliability of the data extraction process. Although measures were taken to ensure annotator agreement, this remains a critical area for ongoing improvement.
- **Scalability of Manual Verification:** While the physician-led verification process ensures high data accuracy, it is resource-intensive and may not be scalable for larger datasets or institutions with limited clinical resources. Future studies should explore the integration of semi-automated verification processes to balance accuracy and scalability.
- **Evaluation Sample Size:** The sample size for verification and validation was determined using a Bayesian statistical approach, which provides a rigorous framework for estimating performance. However, the generalizability of these results to broader datasets and different clinical contexts may require further validation with larger and more diverse samples.
- **Integration Challenges:** The process of integrating NLP-enhanced data into the OMOP CDM framework involves complex data transformations and mappings. Any discrepancies or inconsistencies in this integration process can impact the overall quality and utility of the standardized data. Ongoing efforts to streamline and optimize the integration workflows are essential to mitigate these risks.

5.2 Conclusion

In conclusion, the positive outcomes of this study highlight the significant potential of NLP technologies in revolutionizing clinical data management within the OMOP CDM framework. The demonstrated improvements in data accuracy, quality, and standardization underscore the value of integrating advanced AI methodologies in healthcare data systems. However, addressing the identified limitations through continuous improvement and innovation will be crucial for maximizing the impact and scalability of these technologies in real-world clinical settings.

Acknowledgments

Their collaboration and support were instrumental in the successful execution of this research. We deeply appreciate the efforts and dedication of all the medical professionals involved in this project.

References

- [1] Fernando Martin-Sanchez and Karin Verspoor. Big data in medicine is driving big changes. *Yearbook of medical informatics*, 23(01):14–20, 2014.
- [2] Najia Ahmadi, Yuan Peng, Markus Wolfien, Michéle Zoch, and Martin Sedlmayr. OMOP CDM can facilitate data-driven studies for cancer prediction: A systematic review. *Int. J. Mol. Sci.*, 23(19):11834, October 2022.
- [3] Kristin Kostka, Talita Duarte-Salles, Albert Prats-Urbe, Anthony G Sena, Andrea Pistillo, Sara Khalid, Lana Y H Lai, Asieh Golozar, Thamir M Alshammari, Dalia M Dawoud, Fredrik Nyberg, Adam B Wilcox, Alan Andryc, Andrew Williams, Anna Ostropelets, Carlos Areia, Chi Young Jung, Christopher A Harle, Christian G Reich, Clair Blacketer, Daniel R Morales, David A Dorr, Edward Burn, Elena Roel, Eng Hooi Tan, Evan Minty, Frank DeFalco, Gabriel de Maeztu, Gigi Lipori, Hiba Alghoul, Hong Zhu, Jason A Thomas, Jiang Bian, Jimyung Park, Jordi Martínez Roldán, Jose D Posada, Juan M Banda, Juan P Horcajada, Julianna Kohler, Karishma Shah, Karthik Natarajan, Kristine E Lynch, Li Liu, Lisa M Schilling, Martina Recalde, Matthew Spotnitz, Mengchun Gong, Michael E Matheny, Neus Valveny, Nicole G Weiskopf, Nigam Shah, Osaid Alser, Paula Casajust, Rae Woong Park, Robert Schuff, Sarah Seager, Scott L DuVall, Seng Chan You, Seokyoung Song, Sergio Fernández-Bertolín, Stephen Fortin, Tanja Magoc, Thomas Falconer, Vignesh Subbian, Vojtech Huser, Waheed-Ul-Rahman Ahmed, William Carter, Yin Guan, Yankuic Galvan, Xing He, Peter R Rijnbeek, George Hripsak, Patrick B Ryan, Marc A Suchard, and Daniel Prieto-Alhambra. Unraveling COVID-19: A large-scale characterization of 4.5 million COVID-19 cases us-

ing CHARYBDIS. *Clin. Epidemiol.*, 14:369–384, March 2022.

- [4] European Commission. European Health Data Space — health.ec.europa.eu. https://health.ec.europa.eu/ehealth-digital-health-and-care/european-health-data-space_en. [Accessed 14-09-2024].
- [5] Paula Chocrón, Alvaro Abella, and Gabriel de Maeztu. Contextmel: Classifying contextual modifiers in clinical text. *Sociedad Española para el Procesamiento del Lenguaje Natural*, 2020(65):45–52, 2020.
- [6] Martina Carres, Monica Arrué, and Gabriel Maeztu. Automated concept mapping system for omop using vector representations and cross-hospital mapping. *OHDSI European Symposium 2023*, June 2023.
- [7] Charmaine S. Tam, Janice Gullick, Aldo Saavedra, Stephen T. Vernon, Gemma A. Figtree, Clara K. Chow, Michelle A. Cretikos, Richard W. Morris, Maged William, Jonathan A. Morris, and David B Brieger. Combining structured and unstructured data in emrs to create clinically-defined emr-derived cohorts. *BMC Medical Informatics and Decision Making*, 21, 2020.
- [8] Maryam Tayefi, Phuong D. Ngo, Taridzo Chomutare, Hercules Dalianis, Elisa Salvi, Andrius Budrionis, and Fred Godtliessen. Challenges and opportunities beyond structured data in analysis of electronic health records. *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Computational Statistics*, 13, 2021.
- [9] Umashankar Upadhyay, Anton Gradisek, Usman Iqbal, Eshita Dhar, Yu-Chuan Li, and Shabbir Syed-Abdul. Call for the responsible artificial intelligence in the healthcare. *BMJ Health Care Inform.*, 30(1):e100920, December 2023.
- [10] Elisa Henke, Michele Zoch, Yuan Peng, Ines Reinecke, Martin Sedlmayr, and Franziska Bathelt. Conceptual design of a generic data harmonization process for OMOP common data model. *BMC Med. Inform. Decis. Mak.*, 24(1):58, February 2024.
- [11] Lixuan Yang and Dario Rossi. Quality monitoring and assessment of deployed deep learning models for network aiops. *IEEE Network*, 35:84–90, 2021.
- [12] Hien T Nguyen, Phuc H Duong, and Erik Cambria. Learning short-text semantic similarity with word embeddings and external knowledge sources. *Knowledge-Based Systems*, 182:104842, 2019.
- [13] Maria Quijada, Maria Vivó, Álvaro Abella-Bascarán, Paula Chocrón, and Gabriel de Maeztu. A framework for false negative detection in ner/nel. *Natural Language Processing and Information Systems: 27th International Conference on Applications of Natural Language to Information Systems, NLDB 2022, Valencia, Spain, June 15–17, 2022, Proceedings*, page 323–330, 2022.
- [14] Tiffany J Callahan, Alan E Bauck, David Bertoch, Jeff Brown, Ritu Khare, Patrick B Ryan, Jenny Staab, Meredith N Zozus, and Michael G Kahn. A comparison of data quality assessment checks in six data sharing networks. *EGEMS (Wash., DC)*, 5(1):8, June 2017.
- [15] Michael G Kahn, Tiffany J Callahan, Juliana Barnard, Alan E Bauck, Jeff Brown, Bruce N Davidson, Hossein Estiri, Carsten Goerg, Erin Holve, Steven G Johnson, Siaw-Teng Liaw, Marianne Hamilton-Lopez, Daniella Meeker, Toan C Ong, Patrick Ryan, Ning Shang, Nicole G Weiskopf, Chunhua Weng, Meredith N Zozus, and Lisa Schilling. A harmonized data quality assessment terminology and framework for the secondary use of electronic health record data. *EGEMS (Wash., DC)*, 4(1):1244, September 2016.
- [16] Ramón Margalef. Information theory in ecology, 1958.